

NOSTRUM

Optimizing Floating Offshore Wind Turbines For Use In The Mediterranean Sea

DETAILED MET-OCEAN CONDITIONS
FOR WIND TURBINE DESIGN

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ente beneficiario

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1. Introduction and Scope

The design and analysis of floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) require a comprehensive understanding of the environmental conditions to which these systems are subjected throughout their operational lifetime. This study focuses on the Sicily Med Wind site as a representative location within the Mediterranean Sea, leveraging its unique metocean conditions to develop tailored Design Load Cases (DLCs). Milestone 2 specifically addresses the definition of these DLCs, building on the identification of site characteristics, including seabed profiles and statistical descriptions of wind and sea conditions. The study ensures relevance to local environmental conditions while maintaining applicability across the broader Mediterranean basin. The methodology integrates site-specific environmental data with advanced modelling approaches to ensure realistic and robust simulations for power production and structural safety evaluations. Offshore wind turbines face not only varying wind conditions but also dynamic sea states, which influence their performance and structural integrity. To capture these complexities, this activity emphasizes a multidisciplinary approach to site characterization. Following international standards, key metocean variables—such as wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period, and wind/wave misalignment—are statistically analyzed using long-term hindcast data from the ERA5 database. This data works as the foundation for generating space-time variable wind inflows through atmospheric boundary layer models and synthetic turbulence, ensuring high fidelity in the representation of turbine inflow conditions.

The definition of DLCs builds upon these site-specific environmental conditions to establish a matrix of test cases for evaluating the performance and structural robustness of the turbine. This process extends beyond the baseline requirements of IEC 61400-3, incorporating tailored DLCs that account for the unique metocean conditions of the Sicily Med Wind site and the surrounding Mediterranean region. The DLC matrix covers a wide spectrum of scenarios, including normal operating conditions, extreme environmental loads, fatigue analysis, and system responses during start-up, shutdown, and protection manoeuvres. This tailored approach ensures that the digital wind turbine models are rigorously tested for both power production and structural safety under realistic Mediterranean conditions.

By combining detailed site characterization specific to the Sicily Med Wind site with a robust DLC definition, this milestone provides a critical step toward the design and optimization of FOWTs for the Mediterranean Sea. The results not only enhance the reliability of turbine performance but also ensure compliance with international standards, supporting the development of sustainable and efficient floating wind energy solutions tailored to this region.

2. Methods

The methodology employed in this study is structured to transition from environmental characterization to dynamic simulation, ensuring a seamless integration of met-ocean data into turbine performance analysis. Building on the statistical analyses conducted in activity one, the defined Design Load Cases (DLCs) were systematically implemented to simulate the turbine's response to site-specific conditions at the "Sicily MedWind" installation site.

The first step involved processing long-term hindcast data to derive probabilistic models for key environmental variables—wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period, and wind-wave

misalignment—using advanced statistical techniques, such as hierarchical modeling and the I-FORM strategy. These models were used to generate the inflow conditions needed for dynamic simulations.

In the second step, the DLCs were applied to the digital wind turbine model, incorporating Normal Sea State (NSS) and Severe Sea State (SSS) scenarios. Numerical simulations were conducted to assess the turbine’s performance under both normal operating and extreme conditions, evaluating fatigue loads, extreme responses, and operational safety. The methodology leverages previous research and standards, including the FLOATECH EU project and IEC 61400-3 guidelines, while tailoring the DLCs to the unique met-ocean conditions of the Mediterranean.

This structured approach allows for the step-by-step integration of environmental data into turbine simulations, ensuring that the results align with both international standards and the specific requirements of Mediterranean offshore installations.

2.1 Methodology for Met-Ocean Data Analysis and Scaling

Method is explained in detail in [1]. ERA5 data from 1999-2023 (25 years) is used. ERA5 data is available on a $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ regular grid offshore. As such, the grid point with latitude 37.5° and longitude 11.5° was chosen. Data is available at 100 m above sea level. It was scaled to 170 m using a power law with exponent of 0.12.

Table 1: Characteristics of the site off the Sicilian coast in the Mediterranean Sea

Site	Coordinates	Water depth
Sicily MedWind	37.7558° N 11.6371° W	-400 m

2.2 Met-Ocean Conditions for “Sicily MedWind” Installation Site

Four environmental variables are used to describe the installation site: Wind speed (U), Significant Wave Height (H_s), Peak Spectral Period (T_p), and wind-wave misalignment (M_{WW}). Wind is considered to be aligned with the platform (0° heading), wind-wave misalignment affects wave direction only. This simplification is considered to be in-line with the objectives of this project.

Scatter data for the four environmental variables is shown in Figure 1.

DLC 1.6 can be design-driving in many cases. In this DLC the turbine is simulated under normal operation in 50-year severe waves. According to IEC 61400-3 (2019) [2], the met-ocean conditions corresponding to the design situation can be compute using a 2D contour of wind speed and significant wave height.

The 2D contours are computed using the I-FORM strategy (IEC 61400-3, Annex G) [2]with the methods developed by Haselsteiner et al. [3]. The long-term probability is expressed as a function of the wind speed and significant wave height as:

$$f_{U,H_s}(U, H_s) = f_U(U)f_{H_s}(H_s|U) \quad (1)$$

Wind speed and significant wave height are modeled with a 3-parameter Weibull distribution:

$$f(x) = \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}\right)^\delta \quad (2)$$

δ is considered a fit parameter for the wind speed distribution, while a fixed value of $\delta = 5$ is used for the significant wave height, in line with Haselsteiner et al.

Figure 1: Wind-wave-wind misalignment scatter plots from ERA5 lat: 37.5 lon: 11.5, 1999-2023 (25 yrs)

Figure 2: iso-probability contours of wind speed / significant wave height and 1-year and 50-year return period environmental contours using the distributions proposed by Haselsteiner et al. [3].

The quality of fit for the two variables is shown in Figure 3 in the Q-Q plots. While good fit is noted for wind speed, a discrepancy between the model and data is shown at high significant wave heights. In an attempt to improve this agreement δ is varied. The results are shown in Figure 4. The effect is significant for the 50-year contours, but varying δ does not improve the Q-Q plots.

Figure 3: (top) Goodness of fit of exponentiated Weibull parameters of dependent variable (significant wave height), (bottom) Q-Q plots for wind speed and significant wave height. Exponentiated Weibull distributions

Figure 4: Scatter plots and relative Q-Q plots of wind speed – significant wave height environmental contours

Changing the underlying PDFs improves agreement in the Q-Q plots at higher significant wave heights, although at lower wind speeds and significant wave height agreement is worse. This is confirmed also from a visual comparison with the I-FORM contours (Figure 5). The contours derived in Figure 5 use a Weibull distribution significant wave height, which is considered independent (eq. 2) and for the wind speed, which is conditioned on the significant wave height. The Weibull distribution is shown in eq. 3:

$$f(x) = 1 - e\left[-\left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^\beta\right] \quad (3)$$

In summary, the use of the hierarchical model proposed by Haselsteriner et al. [3], which makes use of two exponentiated Weibull distributions, is preferred. The Exponent of the wind speed distribution is fixed to the value of $\delta = 5$ as suggested in Haselsteriner et al. [3] as this value results in a conservative estimate of the environmental contours, as shown in Fig. 4. This contour is preferred over the DNV-GL suggested distributions as the former provides a better fit at lower wind speeds, which are important for correct estimation of the Severe Sea State (SSS) in DLC 1.6.

Figure 5: 1-year and 50-year wind speed – H_s contours using the “DNV-GL” suggested PDFs

Figure 6: (top) Goodness of fit of exponentiated Weibull parameters of dependent variable (significant wave height), (bottom) Q-Q plots for wind speed and significant wave height. “DNV-GL” distributions

Normal Sea Conditions (Normal Sea State – NSS), require the definition of the expected values of the sea state parameters for each wind speed. For the purpose, a 4D hierarchical model is built. The wind speed is considered independent, significant wave height and wind-wave misalignment are conditioned on the wind speed and peak spectral period is conditioned on the significant wave height, as this is a characteristic of the sea state. The resulting expected values of significant wave height and peak spectral period are shown in Figure 7. The goodness of fit of the distributions in the hierarchical model to the data are shown in Figure 8. Good fit is noted for all environmental variables with the exception of significant wave height, where deviations at higher H_s can be noted, in line with the U- H_s environmental contours discussed previously. Wave heights of over 6 m occur at very high wind speed at the installation site and are thus relatively rare. As such the highlighted discrepancy is not a concern for the current study.

Figure 7: Expected values of significant wave height as a function of the wind speed and of peak spectral period as a function of significant wave height.

Figure 8: (top) Goodness of fit of hierarchical model detailed in [1]. (bottom) Q-Q plots for U , H_s , T_p and M_{ww} .

2.3 Currents and their role in reference site selection

Currents play a fundamental role in determining the feasibility and performance of floating offshore wind turbines, particularly for mooring system stability and turbine dynamics. For the selected reference sites—Sicily MedWind—current characteristics were carefully analyzed alongside wind and wave conditions. The current data for these sites was obtained using hourly data from 2024, sourced from the EU Copernicus Marine Service which provides high-resolution forecasts of sea water velocities in the Mediterranean (1). The analysis focused on time-series data for specific geographic locations. The dataset includes eastward (u_0) and northward (v_0) components of the current, which were used to compute the total sea water velocity and its temporal variations. From this data, minimum, maximum, and average velocities were derived, forming the basis for calculating current forces in future simulations of the floating wind turbine. The results are shown in the Table 2 below in which are presented the mean, maximum and minimum values obtained from the analysis.

Table 2: Summary of current velocities at the Sicily site, showing the mean, maximum, and minimum sea current velocities derived from hourly data for 2024.

Mean sea current velocity (\bar{x})	Max sea current value	Min sea current value
0.201 m/s	0.788 m/s	0.001 m/s

Figure 9: Time series of sea water velocity (swv) at the Sicily site for 2024, showing temporal variations throughout the year (1)

In compliance with IEC 61400-3-1:2019 guidelines, the analysis distinguishes between sub-surface currents, wind-generated near-surface currents, and their combined effects under the Normal Current Model (NCM) and Extreme Current Model (ECM). Sub-surface currents were modelled using a power law to describe the variation of current velocity $U_{ss}(z)$ with depth, following the equation:

$$U_{ss}(z) = U_{ss}(0) \left[\frac{(z + d)}{d} \right]^{1/7}$$

while wind-generated currents were characterized by a linear distribution of velocity,

$$U_w(z) = U_w(0) \left(1 + \frac{z}{20} \right)$$

decreasing from the surface to zero at a depth of 20m below the still water level (SWL).

However, considering the Sicily MedWind site's very deep-water characteristics, where water depths exceed 400 meters, only the depth-independent current velocity was considered in the analysis. This simplification aligns with the IEC guidelines, which permit site-specific adjustments based on the influence of currents. The depth-independent velocity was set as the average total current velocity derived from the hourly data analysis.

To account for extreme conditions as specified by IEC 61400-3-1:2019, the 50-year and 1-year return period current velocities were calculated using statistical analysis of the time-series data. For the 50-year return period, the Gumbel distribution:

$$Vt = \mu - \sigma \cdot \ln \left(-\ln \left(1 - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right)$$

was applied to extrapolate the -extreme value: $\mu(x)$ and $\sigma(x)$, where:

- $\mu(x)$ is the mean velocity of the dataset (calculated as 0.201 m/s);
- $\sigma(x)$ is the standard deviation of the dataset (calculated as 0.134).

The resulting 50-year return period velocity was 0.51 m/s.

For the 1-year return period, where direct statistical modelling is not feasible due to the nature of the data, the mean velocity of the dataset was used as a proxy. This assumption aligns with engineering practises for frequently occurring events. By combining these results with the depth-independent velocity simplifications, the analysis ensures a robust understanding of the current impacts on floating

wind turbine performance under both normal and extreme conditions applied for the Mediterranean Sea.

3. Definition of the Design Load Cases

The Design Load Cases (DLCs) are defined to evaluate the operational performance and structural integrity of floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) under different environmental conditions. These cases are designed in compliance with IEC 61400-3 (2019) guidelines for offshore wind turbine design and are further customized to address the met-ocean conditions of the Mediterranean Sea. The DLC framework incorporates both normal operational conditions and extreme environmental conditions, to ensure comprehensive evaluation.

Below are the summary tables of the analyzed DLCs, to view the complete data please consult the Appendix A: Detailed Design Load Cases.

The first group of DLCs analyzed are those representing normal working conditions – DLC1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.6 – critical for assessing the aerodynamic, hydrodynamic and structural responses of floating offshore wind turbines. As summarized in Table 3, DLC1.1 evaluates turbine behaviour under normal turbulent wind conditions, with wind speeds ranging from cut-in to cut-out values. Wave parameters, derived from Normal Sea State (NSS) conditions, provide a representative characterization of moderate sea environments, ensuring realistic and reliable input for the simulation.

Table 3: Summary of environmental conditions for DLC1.1 simulation, showing the variation ranges for wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period, its minimum and maximum values and the sea current velocity.

U100 (m/s)	Hs (m)	Tp (s)	Tp min (s)	Tp max (s)	Mean current vel (m/s)
1 : 25	0.5 : 5.6	4.7 : 10.5	2.5 : 9.4	8.1 : 11.7	0.201

DLC1.2 focuses on evaluating turbine behavior under normal turbulent wind conditions coupled with a wide range of wave scenarios, including varying degrees of wave propagation misalignment. Wind speeds span the operational range from cut-in to rated, while wave conditions are characterized by Normal Sea State (NSS) parameters. The misalignment between wind and wave directions is systematically varied to reflect realistic offshore conditions typically from -180 to 180 degrees, some examples are summarized in Table 4. This comprehensive analysis is critical for understanding the impact of complex environmental interactions on turbine performance and structural loading.

Table 4: Examples of environmental conditions analysed for DLC 1.2, including wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period and wave propagation misalignment angles.

U100 (m/s)	Hs (m)	Tp (s)	Misalignment (deg)
5	1	4	-150
7	1	6	90
11	3	6	30
17	5	10	30
19	3	6	-30
21	5	10	-30
23	5	10	30

DLC1.3 evaluates turbine behaviour under extreme atmospheric conditions by employing the Extreme Turbulence Model (ETM), as prescribed in the standard. The wind conditions remain within the operational range, from cut-ins to cut-out wind speeds, and wave parameters are derived from Normal Sea State (NSS) conditions, consistent with DLC1.1. (see Table 3). This case differs primarily in its focus on the impact of severe turbulence on the turbine’s aerodynamic and structural responses.

Finally, DLC1.6 evaluates turbine performance under severe environmental conditions, simulating operations with a 50-year return period wave height and peak spectral period. A summary of the environmental conditions analysed is presented in Table 4.

Table 5: Summary of environmental conditions for DLC1.6 simulation, showing the variation ranges for wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period, its minimum and maximum values and the sea current velocity.

U100 (m/s)	Hs (m)	Tp (s)	Tp min (s)	Tp max (s)	Mean current vel (m/s)
1 : 25	3.7 : 8.6	8.9 : 12.6	7.5 : 11.5	10.7 : 13.4	0.201

The last set of DLCs analysed is the Parked (standstill or idling) design situation. In the DLC 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3, the wind turbine's ultimate loads are analysed under extreme environmental conditions. These scenarios simulate the rotor in a parked or idling state, capturing the dynamic responses to combined wind, wave, and current loads. To meet the design requirements, the simulations utilize turbulent wind inflow conditions modelled by the Extreme Wind Model (EWM), coupled with stochastic sea states characterized by non-linear wave kinematics. For DLC 6.1 and 6.2, the combination of extreme wind and wave conditions corresponds to a global return period of 50 years. Conversely, DLC 6.3 evaluates an extreme wind condition with a 1-year return period combined with extreme yaw misalignment.

Table 6: Summary of environmental parameters for 1-year and 50-year return periods, including wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period, and the sea current velocity representing the extreme conditions analyzed for DLC 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3.

	Uw (m/s)	Hs (m)	Tp mean (s)	Tp min (s)	Tp max (s)	Mean current vel (m/s)
1 yr	26.6	7.1	12.3	9.9	14.6	0.201
50 yrs	31.2	9.7	14.3	11.6	17.1	0.51

4. Simulation framework and implementation

The simulations for the defined Design Load Cases (DLCs) were carried out using a Python-based framework designed to automate and streamline the preparation, execution, and management of simulation cases for the IEA 15MW wind turbine model mounted on the UMaine VoltornUS-S semi-submersible platform. The framework was adapted to meet the specific requirements of this study, particularly for floating platform simulations. Key modifications were implemented to handle environmental conditions specific to the Mediterranean, including the ability to dynamically adjust wind and hydrodynamic input files based on the characteristics of each DLC.

This framework enables efficient handling of a large number of load cases by automating input file customization and ensuring consistent initialization for each simulation. Its structure leverages parallel processing to reduce computational time significantly, making it practical to evaluate

extensive design spaces. Pre-existing input file templates were adapted for this work to account for changes in turbine configuration, including blade and airfoil adjustments for optimized designs. Three design configurations were tested: one with the reference rotor radius and optimized blade profiles, and two others featuring 5% and 10% increases in rotor radius, respectively, with corresponding optimizations in chord and twist distributions. The framework integrates tools such as TurbSim for generating turbulent wind fields and HydroDyn for modeling hydrodynamic conditions, ensuring robust and detailed simulations. Each simulation instance is organized in dedicated directories to maintain traceability and clarity in results. By adapting the framework for floating platform simulations, it has been possible to comprehensively evaluate the aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and structural performance of the turbine across a range of environmental conditions, providing critical insights into the suitability of designs for Mediterranean applications.

5. Computational Efficiency and Justification of Approach

The simulations conducted for the defined Design Load Cases (DLCs) represent a critical step in assessing the aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and structural performance of the wind turbine and its floating platform under Mediterranean conditions. Each simulation, corresponding to a specific DLC and design configuration, required approximately two hours to complete for all 25 analysed wind speeds and each simulated for 3600 seconds of simulation per wind speed. This computational efficiency was achieved by leveraging the OpenFAST code on a multiprocessing computing system with the parallel use of 16 processors. The design of the Python-based script was instrumental in this process, enabling the simultaneous execution of multiple wind speed simulations within a DLC, which significantly reduced waiting times. Without parallelization, each DLC simulation would have taken at least three times longer, making the process far less practical.

Additionally, the decision to use a single random seed for the 3600-second simulations, rather than running shorter simulations with multiple seeds, was supported by an analysis of the extracted power for DLC1.1 shown in Figure 10. A detailed plot of the power output over the simulation period demonstrated consistent and reliable results across all three design configurations considered. The analysis confirmed that as the rotor radius increased, the power extracted at the same wind speed also increased, stabilizing at the rated speed due to the action of the controller. This trend was evident for all designs and further validated the use of a single seed for long-duration simulations, as it was sufficient to capture the dynamic behaviour of the turbine under normal operating conditions.

Figure 10: Power curves for the three design configurations (Rbase, R05, R10) under DLC1.1 conditions, showing the relationship between wind speed and extracted power.

This approach not only streamlined the simulation process but also ensured that the results were robust, representative, and provided critical insights into the performance differences across the tested configurations.

These efficiencies underscore the robustness and scalability of the framework, which not only supports high-fidelity simulations across a large parameter space but also enables their integration into broader optimization workflows. When coupled with optimization algorithms, the framework can be extended to iteratively refine turbine designs by automating the evaluation of design candidates while minimizing computational overhead. This capability ensures the feasibility of exploring extensive design spaces and tailoring turbine configurations to Mediterranean conditions, making the framework a critical component for future optimization efforts aimed at improving performance metrics such as Annual Energy Production (AEP) and structural reliability.

6. Conclusions

The study successfully defined Design Load Cases (DLCs) tailored to the Mediterranean Sea, ensuring that simulations accurately reflect the unique environmental conditions of the selected site. Through comprehensive analysis of long-term ERA5 metocean data and the application of advanced statistical models, key variables such as wind speed, significant wave height, peak spectral period, and wind-wave misalignment were characterized. These parameters formed the basis for a robust simulation framework, integrating tools like TurbSim and HydroDyn to evaluate the aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and structural performance of the IEA 15MW reference turbine mounted on a semi-submersible platform. The automated framework facilitated efficient and accurate analysis of turbine behavior under both normal operational and extreme conditions, providing essential insights into turbine design, control strategy development, and platform evaluation. Overall, the results confirm the suitability of the reference turbine and platform for Mediterranean applications and establish a strong foundation for future optimization efforts within the project.

References

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Appendix A: Detailed Design Load Cases

This appendix presents the complete tables of the Design Load Cases (DLCs) used in this study. These tables provide detailed environmental and operational conditions, including wind speed, significant wave height, and peak spectral period, which were applied in the simulations for evaluating the aerodynamic, hydrodynamic, and structural performance of the turbine and platform. The data complements the summary provided in the main body of the report, offering a comprehensive view of the scenarios analysed. These tables are intended to support a deeper

understanding of the input parameters and their role in defining the turbine's dynamic behaviour under Mediterranean conditions.

Table A1: Environmental conditions for DLC1.1 (normal turbulence model) and DLC1.3 (extreme turbulence model). The table includes the values of significant wave height (H_s), peak spectral period (T_p), minimum peak spectral period ($T_p \text{ min}$), and maximum peak spectral period ($T_p \text{ max}$), representing normal sea state (NSS) conditions applied in the simulations.

	$U100$ (m/s)	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	$T_p \text{ min}$ (s)	$T_p \text{ max}$ (s)
0	1	0.47222	4.741281	2.536008	8.141649
1	2	0.491411	4.788693	2.574877	8.190841
2	3	0.529078	4.878928	2.650226	8.281829
3	4	0.58461	5.00586	2.759295	8.404077
4	5	0.657499	5.162992	2.899344	8.546395
5	6	0.747351	5.344359	3.067944	8.698855
6	7	0.85389	5.544975	3.263072	8.853768
7	8	0.976941	5.760916	3.483054	9.005908
8	9	1.116415	5.989223	3.726443	9.152317
9	10	1.272295	6.227722	3.991884	9.291907
10	11	1.444612	6.474835	4.277992	9.425019
11	12	1.633436	6.729424	4.583253	9.553014
12	13	1.838854	6.990648	4.905967	9.677908
13	14	2.060969	7.257866	5.244219	9.80208
14	15	2.299882	7.530562	5.595891	9.928034
15	16	2.555691	7.808293	5.958697	10.05822
16	17	2.828486	8.090659	6.330242	10.19491
17	18	3.118346	8.377279	6.708099	10.34009
18	19	3.425339	8.667786	7.089893	10.49542
19	20	3.749521	8.961822	7.473377	10.66223
20	21	4.09094	9.259042	7.856512	10.84145
21	22	4.449631	9.559118	8.237516	11.03369
22	23	4.825624	9.861739	8.614914	11.23923
23	24	5.218941	10.16662	8.987549	11.45806
24	25	5.629598	10.4735	9.354588	11.6899

Table A2: Environmental conditions for DLC1.2 (normal operating conditions with wind-wave misalignment). The table includes the values of significant wave height (H_s), peak spectral period (T_p), misalignment angles between wind and wave directions, and the probability of occurrence

	$U100$ (m/s)	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	Mis (deg)	P
0	5	1	4	-150	0.001365
1	5	1	4	-90	0.003069
2	5	1	4	-30	0.025491
3	5	1	4	30	0.038788
4	5	1	4	90	0.006729
5	5	1	4	150	0.001724
6	5	1	6	-150	0.003702
7	5	1	6	-90	0.006781
8	5	1	6	-30	0.019985
9	5	1	6	30	0.024716

MISSIONE 4
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RICERCA

10	5	1	6	90	0.007551
11	5	1	6	150	0.00391
12	5	1	8	-150	0.002177
13	5	1	8	-90	0.003428
14	5	1	8	-30	0.006923
15	5	1	8	30	0.007362
16	5	1	8	90	0.002866
17	5	1	8	150	0.001369
18	5	1	10	-90	0.000808
19	5	1	10	-30	0.001384
20	5	1	10	30	0.001889
21	5	1	10	90	0.000737
22	7	1	4	-90	0.000841
23	7	1	4	-30	0.027998
24	7	1	4	30	0.040739
25	7	1	4	90	0.002899
26	7	1	6	-150	0.001865
27	7	1	6	-90	0.004023
28	7	1	6	-30	0.023961
29	7	1	6	30	0.031644
30	7	1	6	90	0.004113
31	7	1	6	150	0.001884
32	7	1	8	-150	0.001369
33	7	1	8	-90	0.003291
34	7	1	8	-30	0.00858
35	7	1	8	30	0.009577
36	7	1	8	90	0.001691
37	7	1	8	150	0.000888
38	7	1	10	-30	0.001667
39	7	1	10	30	0.002323
40	9	1	4	-30	0.023588
41	9	1	4	30	0.031752
42	9	1	4	90	0.00093
43	9	1	6	-90	0.001492
44	9	1	6	-30	0.023243
45	9	1	6	30	0.033183
46	9	1	6	90	0.001573
47	9	1	6	150	0.00068
48	9	1	8	-90	0.002092
49	9	1	8	-30	0.008798
50	9	1	8	30	0.008547
51	9	1	8	90	0.000878
52	9	1	10	-30	0.00102
53	9	1	10	30	0.001643
54	9	3	8	-30	0.001544
55	9	3	8	30	0.001719

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56	9	3	10	-30	0.00119
57	9	3	10	30	0.000978
58	11	1	4	-30	0.015423
59	11	1	4	30	0.019843
60	11	1	6	-30	0.023512
61	11	1	6	30	0.030831
62	11	1	8	-90	0.001124
63	11	1	8	-30	0.006488
64	11	1	8	30	0.004505
65	11	1	10	-30	0.000619
66	11	1	10	30	0.000765
67	11	3	6	30	0.000642
68	11	3	8	-30	0.005336
69	11	3	8	30	0.006186
70	11	3	10	-30	0.002092
71	11	3	10	30	0.001842
72	13	1	4	-30	0.006002
73	13	1	4	30	0.00722
74	13	1	6	-30	0.017638
75	13	1	6	30	0.020702
76	13	1	8	-30	0.002182
77	13	1	8	30	0.000954
78	13	3	6	-30	0.00263
79	13	3	6	30	0.003518
80	13	3	8	-30	0.010753
81	13	3	8	30	0.010238
82	13	3	10	-30	0.002083
83	13	3	10	30	0.001875
84	15	1	4	-30	0.00094
85	15	1	4	30	0.001185
86	15	1	6	-30	0.007244
87	15	1	6	30	0.009449
88	15	3	6	-30	0.004675
89	15	3	6	30	0.005412
90	15	3	8	-30	0.01096
91	15	3	8	30	0.010049
92	15	3	10	-30	0.001969
93	15	3	10	30	0.001521
94	17	1	6	-30	0.001166
95	17	1	6	30	0.001936
96	17	3	6	-30	0.003254
97	17	3	6	30	0.004014
98	17	3	8	-30	0.007645
99	17	3	8	30	0.006625
100	17	3	10	-30	0.001809
101	17	3	10	30	0.001261

102	17	5	10	-30	0.000718
103	17	5	10	30	0.000793
104	19	3	6	-30	0.001015
105	19	3	6	30	0.001138
106	19	3	8	-30	0.003934
107	19	3	8	30	0.003268
108	19	5	10	-30	0.001388
109	19	5	10	30	0.001412
110	21	3	8	-30	0.001011
111	21	3	8	30	0.000963
112	21	5	10	-30	0.001204
113	21	5	10	30	0.001497
114	23	5	10	30	0.000713

Table A3: Environmental conditions for DLC1.6 (severe sea state). The table includes the values of significant wave height (H_s), peak spectral period (T_p), minimum peak spectral period ($T_p \text{ min}$), and maximum peak spectral period ($T_p \text{ max}$), representing severe environmental conditions with a 50-year return period.

	$U100$ (m/s)	H_s (m)	T_p (s)	$T_p \text{ min}$ (s)	$T_p \text{ max}$ (s)
0	1	3.743601	8.95656	7.466549	10.65915
1	2	3.829488	9.032525	7.564978	10.70387
2	3	3.851817	9.052145	7.590349	10.71554
3	4	3.906945	9.10036	7.652604	10.7444
4	5	4.004281	9.184728	7.761211	10.79561
5	6	4.137315	9.298511	7.906981	10.86608
6	7	4.297176	9.433009	8.078173	10.9515
7	8	4.475914	9.580653	8.264608	11.04793
8	9	4.666688	9.735221	8.458016	11.15188
9	10	4.866754	9.894158	8.654907	11.26195
10	11	5.074056	10.05562	8.852791	11.37704
11	12	5.287024	10.21827	9.049898	11.49628
12	13	5.505511	10.38193	9.245923	11.61954
13	14	5.729989	10.54688	9.441139	11.74701
14	15	5.961511	10.71379	9.636277	11.87923
15	16	6.199847	10.88238	9.830954	12.01597
16	17	6.445393	11.05283	10.02534	12.15736
17	18	6.699157	11.22572	10.22004	12.30385
18	19	6.961106	11.40088	10.41485	12.45531
19	20	7.230249	11.57753	10.60893	12.61099
20	21	7.506946	11.75583	10.80247	12.77094
21	22	7.7893	11.93449	10.99414	12.9339
22	23	8.075779	12.11254	11.18304	13.09881
23	24	8.363657	12.28836	11.36761	13.26395
24	25	8.648769	12.45958	11.54559	13.4268

Table A4: Environmental conditions for DLC6.1, DLC6.2, and DLC6.3 (extreme sea state). The table includes the values of significant wave height (H_s), peak spectral period (T_p), minimum peak spectral period ($T_p \text{ min}$), and maximum peak spectral period ($T_p \text{ max}$), representing extreme sea states for both 1-year and 50-year return periods.

	U_w (m/s)	H_s (m)	$T_p \text{ mean}$ (s)	$T_p \text{ min}$ (s)	$T_p \text{ max}$ (s)
1 yr	26.60345	7.092929	12.28701	9.948651	14.62537
50 yrs	31.19707	9.651482	14.33278	11.60509	17.06047